

Interfacial Reaction and Tensile Strength of Monofilament Composites with Al-base Matrix.

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Abstract

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of thermal exposure on interfacial reactions and the tensile properties in SiC fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composites. To simplify the situation, monofilament composites were produced by coating a pure aluminum on the fiber surface using a vapor deposition method. A statistical approach was employed to analyze the tension test data for the precision of the measurements.

The tensile strength of β -SiC fibers decreases with increasing the fiber length. This size effect was more pronounced in the SiC fibers compared with the other fibers. The tensile strength of the SiC and Carbon monofilament composites produced by coating a pure aluminum on the fiber surface was significantly deteriorated after exposure at temperatures of 500 and 450 °C, respectively. This decrease in the tensile strength is attributed to interfacial reaction at the matrix-fiber interface. Weibull modulus m value in both SiC monofilament composites tended to be decreased interfacial reaction zone.

1. Introduction

Interfacial characteristics of metal matrix composites are most important factors controlling many of the mechanical properties. Therefore, a considerable amount of research effort has been invested to study interfacial problems of metal matrix composites (1,2). For SiC fiber reinforced aluminum composites, it has been recognized (3,4,5,6) that interfacial reactions occur at the temperature range of 500 - 750 °C based upon the type of matrix aluminum alloys and that interfacial reaction products were identified as brittle SiO and Al C compounds. However, the correlations between interfacial reactions and the mechanical properties have not been fully established yet.(7)

The main objective of this study is to find the effect of thermal exposure on interfacial reactions and the tensile properties in SiC fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composites. To simplify the situation, monofilament composites were produced by coating a pure aluminum on the fiber surface using a vapor deposition method. A statistical approach was employed to analyze the tension test data for the precision of the measurements.

2. Experimental Procedure

2-1. Materials

As described in Table 1, β -SiC fiber (Nicalon : Japanese Carbon Co.) Matrix were prepared from commercial pure Al.

2-2. Specimen Fabrication and Thermal Exposure

Monofilament composites were produced by coating matrix materials on the fiber surface using a vapor deposition method in a vacuum of 8×10^{-5} torr. The thickness of the coated layer was 3-4 μm for SiC fibers. In order to investigate matrix-fiber interfacial reactions and their effect on the tensile strength, the monofilament composite fibers were exposed at temperatures ranging from 300 to 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for one hour in a vacuum of 8×10^{-3} torr.

2-3. Tensile Test

Room temperature tension tests were conducted on the fiber specimens according to the ASTM D 3379 specification using a Toyo Baldwin Tension Machine (Model UTM-III-500). The cross head speed was 2 mm/min. for all the fiber specimens. To determine the size effect of uncoated fiber specimens, the gauge length was varied from 5 to 200 mm/min. In the case of Al coated fiber specimens, the gauge length was 30 mm for SiC monofilament composites as shown in Fig.1. For accurate measurements of cross-sectional areas, diameters of the fiber specimens were determined using a micrometer eyepiece (Olympus Model OSM-D2). Figure 1 illustrates the configuration of tension specimens.

2-4. Metallography and Analysis

The monofilament composite fibers were also examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) before and after removal of the coated layer using a 10 percent sodium hydroxide solution. For the identification of interfacial reaction products, the chemistry of matrix-fiber interfaces is being analyzed by Auger electron spectroscopy (AES).

3. Results and Discussion

Since tensile strength data of very brittle materials like SiC fibers exhibit considerable scatter and strong size effect, it is necessary to apply a statistical approach for determining the precision of the measurements and for drawing valid conclusions from the data. It has been recognized that the Weibull distribution is particularly well suited to describing the distribution of the tensile strength of brittle fibers (8,9). The Weibull cumulative distribution function can be given by

$$P(f) = 1 - \exp[-V\{(\sigma - \sigma_u) / \sigma_0\}^m]$$

where $P(f)$ is the probability that fracture occurs at a stress value less than the applied stress σ , V is the volume of fiber, σ_u is the threshold stress (σ for $P(f) = 0$), σ_0 is the normalizing stress (σ for $P(f) = 0.632$), and m is the Weibull modulus.

Figures 2 illustrate the Weibull distribution of uncoated SiC fiber for different gauge lengths. From Figures 2, it can be seen that the Weibull probability plot moves to the left for SiC fibers as the fiber length increases. This indicates a size effect of the fiber specimens that the tensile strength decreases with increasing the fiber length.

To better illustrate the size effect, the data in Figures 2 were replotted as the mean tensile strength versus the fiber length for SiC fibers in Figures 3. Here, the mean tensile strength of SiC fiber length can be determined from a stress value when the Weibull probability, $P(f)$, is 0.5 in Figures 2. From Figures 3, it can be clearly seen that the mean tensile strength decreases with increasing the SiC fiber length. It is also noted from the Figures 3 that the size effect is very pronounced in SiC fibers. Since brittle fracture is controlled, not by an average value of the distribution of cracks, but by the one, most severe crack, the above phenomenon can be explained by the weakest-link concept. As the length of the fiber increases, the total number of cracks also increases and therefore the probability of encountering a severe crack is increased.

Figures 4 show the variation of the mean tensile strength with the thermal exposure temperature for SiC monofilament composites. No pronounced effect of thermal exposure on the mean tensile strength was detected up to an exposure temperature of 400 °C. However, the tensile strength of SiC monofilament composites was significantly deteriorated after the exposure at temperatures of 500 °C. These results suggest that interfacial reactions at matrix-fiber interfaces would occur at temperatures of 500 °C, leading to a significant decrease in the tensile strength of SiC monofilament composites. Scanning electron micrographs of the SiC fiber specimens for different conditions were shown in Figures 5 - 7.

As shown in Figure 5 (a), SiC fibers have smooth surface and diameter of 15 μm . Figure 5 (b) shows that the surface of SiC fibers remains smooth after coating with a pure aluminum. It is noted that the surface of SiC fiber coated with a pure aluminum even after thermal exposure at 500 °C and 600 °C as shown in Figure 6. However, it is found that as shown in Figure 7 (a),(b) and (c), some residual phases on the matrix-fiber interface in specimen exposed at 500 and 600 °C is formed when the coated layer was removed from the fiber surface whereas the specimen exposed at 400 °C does not show any residual phases. These results suggest that some interfacial reaction occur at the matrix-fiber interface at 500 and 600 °C. Therefore, the decrease in the tensile strength of SiC monofilament composites after thermal exposures at 500 and 600 °C can be attributed to the occurrence of this interfacial reaction.

In order to identify the interfacial reaction products, the chemistry at the matrix - fiber interface is being analyzed by Auger Electron Spectroscopy.

4. Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn from this study :

1. The tensile strength of β -SiC fibers decreases with increasing the fiber length. This size effect is very pronounced in the SiC fibers compared with that of other typical fibers.
2. The tensile strength of the SiC monofilament composites produced by coating a pure aluminum on the fiber surface is significantly deteriorated after exposed to the above temperatures of 450 °C. This decrease in the tensile strength is attributed to interfacial reaction at the matrix-fiber interface.

3. Weibull modulus m value in SiC monofilament composites appeared to be decreased with interfacial reaction zone.
4. The interfacial reaction product was observed by scanning electron microscopy when the fiber specimens coated with a pure aluminum were thermal exposed and the coated layer was removed using a 10 percent sodium hydroxide solution.

6. REFERENCES

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$$L > 2000 D$$

L=Gage length, D=Fiber diameter

Figure. 1 Tab showing typical specimen mounting method.

Figure 2 Weibull plots of SiC fiber samples for different lengths.

Fig. 3 Relation between mean tensile strength and SiC fiber length.

Figure 4 Variation in tensile strength of SiC monofilament composites with exposure temperature.

Figure 5 Scanning electron micrographs of SiC fiber.
 (a) SiC fiber (b) SiC/Pure Al

Figure 6 Scanning electron micrographs of SiC/Pure Al composites after thermal exposure.
 (1) 500°C (b) 600°C

Figure 7 Scanning electron micrographs of SiC fiber surfaces in SiC monofilament composites thermal-exposed for 60 min.
 (a) 400°C (b) 500°C (c) 600°C